

English Grammar Proficiency Among Indonesian Postgraduate Students: Identifying Areas for Improvement

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the grammatical challenges faced by postgraduate students and provide practical solutions to address these issues. Employing a descriptive approach, this research examined the implementation of a compulsory TOEFL MOCK Test policy for new postgraduate students. Twenty postgraduate students participated in this study, focusing on the second section of the test, which assesses Structure and Written Expression. The grammatical analysis was informed by the framework outlined in Barron's TOEFL book, 'Practice Exercises for the TOEFL'. The second section comprises questions on word choice, verbs, clauses, agreements, parallel structures, nouns, pronouns, comparison, connectors, modifiers, and redundancy. The findings revealed that the most challenging questions for the students were related to word choice and verbs, with only 45% of the participants (9 out of 20) demonstrating adequate Structure English Competency. The remaining students struggled to answer the structure and written expression questions, resulting in low scores. Overall, the scores of the 20 participants ranged from 330 to 567, with a standard score of 425 for postgraduate students. Based on these results, it is concluded that postgraduate students understand English structure well. By recognizing the significance of English grammatical aspects in academic success, the academic world can take steps to improve language instruction, assessment, and policy, ultimately enhancing students' overall academic performance.

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1. Introduction

English stands as a universal language essential for global communication and understanding. Proficiency in English is paramount for international engagement in academic settings. Notably, assessments like IELTS and TOEFL serve as standardized measures of language abilities. My investigation into the challenges faced by postgraduate students in taking the TOEFL test at Nusa Cendana University's Law Studies program aims to identify grammatical difficulties and offer targeted solutions to elevate English proficiency.

The study delves into specific research questions and aims to yield insights for the development of impactful language support programs and instructional materials. Additionally, the study will provide practical recommendations to bolster students' TOEFL test preparation and enhance language instruction and assessment practices.

The significance of this study is its potential to address the need for tailored language support programs for postgraduate students in the Law Studies program at Nusa Cendana University. By identifying grammatical challenges faced by these students in the TOEFL test, the study can inform targeted interventions to enhance their English proficiency and academic performance.

It can have broader implications for language instruction and assessment practices at the university level and beyond, benefiting language learners and educators globally. Ultimately, the study aims to positively impact the academic success and career prospects of postgraduate students and contribute to the development of effective language support programs.

2. Materials and Method

2.1 TOEFL Test

The abbreviation 'TOEFL' stands for Test of English as a Foreign Language. It is a test designed to measure the English language proficiency of individuals who do not speak English as their first language and who plan to study at colleges and universities where English is the primary medium of instruction. The copyright for this test belongs to the Educational Testing Service (ETS), located in Princeton, New Jersey, USA. ETS is an educational foundation that prepares and administers the TOEFL test. In addition to TOEFL, this organization also produces many other standardized English tests, including the Test of English for International Communication (TOEIC), the Graduate Management Admissions Test (GMAT), and the Graduate Record Exam (GRE) (Educational Testing Service, n.d.; Kunnan, 2009; Liu, 2008; Xi, 2008; Powers, 2010).

While there are several English proficiency tests available, the most popular and accessible one for non-native English speakers worldwide is the TOEFL test. There are numerous advantages to taking the TOEFL test. Test takers take this test for various purposes, such as to increase their chances of being accepted when applying for a job in a multinational or state-owned company. Applicants with high TOEFL scores are more likely to be accepted for the job than those with low scores.

Shahane Renuka (2023), an Indian educator, identified five benefits of taking the TOEFL test: 1) The TOEFL is accepted in around 10,000 universities across 150 countries worldwide. 2) TOEFL scores are considered the most accurate measurement of an individual's English proficiency. 3) TOEFL scores are valid worldwide for 2 years. 4) A valid TOEFL score could support visa applications for Australia and New Zealand for business purposes as well as PR (Permanent Resident) applications. Having a valid TOEFL score of 79 or more can support one's skilled migrant visa application. 5) TOEFL helps to improve one's language skills, both written and verbal (ETS, 2023; Chapelle & Chung, 2023; ETS, 2024; Australian Government Department of Home Affairs, 2023; New Zealand Immigration, 2023; Liu & Chen, 2023; Wagner, 2024; Phakiti, 20203).

Due to the importance of the TOEFL test worldwide, particularly for students in postgraduate programs, the researcher decided to conduct research on the TOEFL test held by the Language Center of Nusa Cendana University to identify the grammar-related issues that affect the test results. This research is expected to help students and colleges improve English proficiency levels through TOEFL MOCK tests.

2.2 Method

This research employed a descriptive approach to analyze the answer sheets of TOEFL Mock tests taken by Law Studies postgraduate students at Nusa Cendana University. The study followed Denzin's (1994) concepts of qualitative research, aiming to describe the natural settings of human beings and interpret phenomena in terms of the meanings people bring to them.

The researcher collected the test results from UNDANA Language Center Kupang and analyzed the number of correct and incorrect answers in the structure and written expression section, categorizing them according to material categories such as verbs, nouns, and clauses. This analysis helped identify the difficulties faced by postgraduate students in taking the TOEFL PBT test and their English proficiency level.

The research was conducted at UNDANA Language Center in Kupang, targeting the TOEFL test results of new postgraduate students of Law Studies. The answer sheets served as the research instrument, and data collection involved documenting the students' answer sheets and scores. The data was analyzed using a four-cycle approach, including data collection, reduction, display, and conclusion drawing/verifying.

The analysis involved reducing the data to identify patterns and themes, displaying the data in charts and narratives, and drawing conclusions about the most difficult problems faced by postgraduate students in taking the TOEFL Mock test. The study aimed to provide insights into the English proficiency level of Law Studies postgraduate students and inform strategies to improve their language skills in the context of globalization.

3. Discussion

Findings of this research described the grammatical aspects in TOEFL Mock Test especially in section 2 about structures and written expressions (Barron's, 2005). Based on the questions and the answer sheets, the researcher classified the wrong and the right answer according to the grammatical aspects. The questions for each student were not same. The questions with FQ01 code differed from the questions with FQ02 code, but these questions contained the same grammatical aspects.

3.1. The Grammatical Difficulties in TOEFL MOCK Test

The most difficult structure for postgraduate students of Law Studies are related to verbs, word choice, clauses, agreement, parallel structures, nouns, pronouns, comparative, connector, modifier, and auxiliary verb.

For example, no one can choose the right answer for the question number 38 in FQ01 which asks about the word choice (appendix FQ01).

Sheep have been domesticated for over 5,000 years ago.

A B C D

The question above requires the students to choose which underlined part is wrong and needs correction in order the sentence to be correct grammatically. Most of the student chose option A, B, and C. None of them chose the option D. The phrase 'years ago' refers to the past. This means that the

tense should be in the simple past tense. In fact, the sentence uses the present perfect tense and that means, the use of 'ago' is not appropriate for this sentence and therefore it should be omitted.

For question number 16 in FQ02, which is about verb, only 2 students chose the correct answer (appendix FQ02).

Neither Professor Johnson nor any other faculty member _____ to apply for the dean's position.

- (A) Intend
- (B) Intends
- (C) Are intending
- (D) Has intend

The correct answer is (B), the verb in the singular form for the third singular person in the simple present tense. The use of neither nor should go with the subject in singular form.

3.2 The Most Difficult Questions in TOEFL MOCK Test

The findings were compiled and presented based on the response sheets of the students in the Law Studies Postgraduate Program. The names of the participants were anonymized to protect their privacy. The researcher identified the top 10 most frequently chosen incorrect answers by the students for each question code (FQ01 and FQ02). A total of 55 questions were examined, with 30 questions in FQ01 and 25 questions in FQ02, which were deemed the most challenging and perplexing for the students to tackle.

Detailed explanations of the grammatical challenges encountered by the postgraduate students in the Law Studies program are available in Table 3 in the appendix.

In FQ01, the 30 questions were ordered as follows: 38, 3, 23, 13, 34, 10, 11, 20, 29, 30, 32, 36, 39, 7, 14, 15, 26, 28, 33, 1, 8, 16, 17, 19, 22, 24, 25, 35, 37, and 40. Each question was ranked from the most challenging to the easiest to answer. The topics of the questions encompassed word choice, verb tenses, and agreement.

As for FQ02, the 25 questions were listed in the following order: 32, 1, 22, 38, 8, 16, 24, 26, 30, 6, 10, 19, 20, 21, 23, 25, 27, 29, 37, 40, 2, 5, 11, 18, and 35, with the most difficult question listed first. The subjects of the questions included parallel structure, verb tenses, agreement, word choice, and dependent clauses.

These 55 questions were selected from a total of 80 questions from FQ01 and FQ02, as they were considered to be the most demanding for the students in the Law Studies program. Further elucidations of the grammatical challenges identified in these questions can be found in the discussion section below.

3.3 The Grammatical Difficulties Faced by Postgraduate Law Students

In FQ01, students were asked to choose one incorrect option to be corrected or changed and the researcher has already ranked the number of questions from the most difficult ones to the easiest question. Starts from number 38. This question was about the word choice (appendix FQ01). For example:

Sheep have been domesticated for over 5,000 years ago.

A B C D

The question above required the students to choose which underlined part was wrong and needed correction in order the sentence to be corrected grammatically. Most of the students chose option A, B, and C. None of them chose the option D. The phrase 'years ago' refers to the past. This means that the tense should be in the simple past tense. In fact, the sentence used the present perfect

tense, and that means, the word 'ago' was not appropriate for this sentence and therefore it should be omitted.

Question number 3 was about superlative (appendix FQ01). For example:

_____ greyhound, can achieve speeds up to thirty-six miles per hour.

- (A) The
- (B) The fastest
- (C) The fastest dog
- (D) The fastest dog, the

The question above required the students to choose which one should be the best answer to fill the blank. Most of the students chose option A, B, and C. None of them chose the option D. Option D was the best answer for the question above. After the superlative, the article 'the' in the phrase refers to the particular noun that is 'greyhound' to complete the sentence. Some students get confused by choosing the other options because they only focused on the superlative words 'the fastest' without seeing the complete sentence to define the complete superlative sentence.

Question number 23 was about verb (appendix FQ01). For example:

Before Richard Bennett accepted the appointment as the prime minister of Canada in 1930, he _____ as a lawyer.

- A. Had achieved a successful
- B. Had been achieved successfully
- C. Had been achieved success
- D. Had achieved success

The best answer was in option D. The sentence structure should be in past perfect tense after the past tense to explain the event had happened before the other event happened. So the formula of the sentence should be had + past participle. Students get confused with the pattern of the past perfect tense in the other options that effect the meaning of the sentence instead of choosing the simple form of past perfect tense that gives appropriate meaning.

Question number 13 was also about verb (appendix FQ01). For example:

Rubber ____ from vulcanized silicones with a high molecular weight was difficult to distinguish from natural rubber.

- A. Is produced
- B. Producing
- C. That produces
- D. Produced

The question above required the students to choose the best verb that was suitable to the sentence. Option D was the best answer to complete the past tense sentence above. Some students get distracted with the options A because of the passive form that was reasonable to choose.

Question number 34 was about redundancy (appendix FQ01). For example:

Ballet performers must be believable actors and actresses as well as experts

dancers.

The question above required the students to analyze carefully the error grammar in the sentence. Option D showed redundancy with the noun 'dancers'. 's' in word 'expert' should be omitted because the word 'expert' functions as an adjective to modify the noun dancers. Some students did not realize the redundancy of the plural form by additions in the word that make them choose the wrong answer.

Question number 10 was about dependent clause (appendix FQ01). For example:

The sentence above was telling about past tense in 1726, the best answer to complete the sentence above was in option B. Question number 17 was about word choice (appendix FQ01). For example:

Soil texture depends on the proportions of clay and sand particles, ___ soil porosity.

- A. Both alter
- B. Which alter
- C. where altered
- D. Although altered

The best subordinate conjunction to complete the clause above is in option B that gives the positive meaning.

Question number 19 was about comparative. For example:

The bones of the elderly are more prone to fractures and splintering ___ of young people.

- A. Than that
- B. Than those
- C. Those than
- D. That than

The only good order of comparative was in option B. The word '*those*' refers to the bones at the first sentence.

Question number 22 was about word choice (appendix FQ01). For example:

Only ___ feathered creatures inhabit the Artic region year around.

- A. Fewer
- B. Fewer than
- C. As few as
- D. A few

The best choice to complete the sentence was D. The word '*a few*' agrees to the uncountable noun '*feathered*'.

Question number 24 was about agreement (appendix FQ01). For example:

Gardeners transplant bushes and flowers by moving them from one place to ____

- A. Other
- B. Others
- C. Another
- D. Each other

The best choice to complete the sentence was option C. The word '*another*' means one other refers to '*one place*'.

Question number 25 was about parallel structure (appendix FQ01). For example:

Museums of natural history are ordinarily ___ by special interest groups created for that purpose.

- A. Owned and operated
- B. They own and operate
- C. Owning and operating
- D. The owner operates

The sentence above was about the history in the past time, thus the best answer was in option A with parallel past verb.

Question number 35 was about word choice (appendix FQ01). For example:

Venus, the second planet from the Sun, is exactly almost the same size as the

A B C D

Earth.

Option C should be corrected by placing the word in order. It should be '*almost exactly*' not '*exactly almost*'.

Question number 37 was about word order (appendix FQ01). For example:

The way a child plays with other children reveals a lots about the child's emotional

A B C

development.

D

The word '*a lots*' in option B should be changed. '*s*' in the word '*lot*' should be omitted. It was incorrect word.

Question number 40 was about noun. For example:

Duke University in North Carolina has an outstanding collecting of the documents

A B

concernig Southern history.

C D

The word '*collecting*' in option B should be changed with the word '*collection*' as a proper noun that modify the word '*documents*'.

The questions above were the most 30 difficult questions for the postgraduate students of Law Studies to answer in TOEFL MOCK Test. They often made mistakes in choosing the correct answer for sentences or clauses and choosing the correct words to complete the sentences. It was because of the lack of grammatical knowledge they acquired. It could be a problem affect the result of the test.

Questions in FQ02 TOEFL MOCK TEST

In FQ02 questions, there were 25 numbers of grammatical difficulties were found by the postgraduate students of Law Study. The questions were ordered from the most difficult questions to the easiest questions to answer. Students were asked to choose one best answer of four options and in some questions, students were asked to choose one incorrect option to be corrected or changed. Number 32 was about word choice (appendix FQ02). For example:

Dresses, skirts, shoes, and children's clothing are advertised at great reduced prices

A B C D

this weekend.

In this question, the word great in option D should be changed with the word '*big*' which was appropriate to the sentence. Most of the students did not realize that they chose the wrong answer except the option D. The lack of knowledge of word choice was the matter in choosing the right one.

Number 1 was about introduction verbal modifier (appendix FQ02). For example:

Captain Henry, ___ crept slowly through the underbrush.

- A. Being remote from the enemy,
- B. Attempting to not encounter the enemy,
- C. Tried to avoid the enemy,
- D. Not involving himself in the enemy,

The best answer for this question was in option A. It is an introductory verbal modifier which was followed by a comma and the noun that was Captain Henry was modified by the phrase '*being remote*

from the enemy'. The incapability of analyzing the grammatical problem affects the right answer chosen by the students.

Number 22 was about verb (appendix FQ02). For example:

_____ better, the team would have been able to defeat the opponent.

- A. If it prepares
- B. If prepares
- C. Preparing
- D. Had it prepared

The best answer to complete the sentence above was the past perfect tense as was option D '*Had it prepared*'. Again, the inability of the students to analyze the grammatical aspect affects the right answer to be chosen.

Number 38 was about modifier (appendix FQ02). For example:

A five-thousand-dollar reward was offered for the capture of the escaped

A B C D
criminals.

The modifier plural noun '*dollars*' should be changed in singular noun to modify the precede noun. Some students get confused by looking at the word '*thousand*' that makes them do not choose the option B.

Number 8 was about parallel structure (appendix FQ02). For example:

Public television stations are different from commercial stations _____.

- A. Because they receive money differently and different types of shows
- B. For money and program types
- C. In the areas of funding and programming
- D. Because the former receives money and has programs differently from the latter

The best answer to complete the sentence above was in the option C. The sentence contains the parallel structure of *-ing* form after the preposition. The parallel structure of *-ing* form seemed easy that made the students did not pay full attention on this grammatical aspect that cause the choosing the wrong answer.

Number 16 was about verb (appendix FQ02). For example:

Neither Professor Johnson nor any other faculty member ___ to apply for the dean's position.

- A. Intended
- B. Intends
- C. Are intending
- D. Has intend

In the question above, the best answer to complete the sentence was in option B. The verb '*intends*' explain the situation that no one wants to apply the position. The verb agreed to the subject to define the simple present tense. The lack of analyzing the form of tenses caused the students to misunderstanding the meaning of the sentence and make a wrong decision.

Number 24 was about comparative (appendix FQ02). For example:

The curriculum at the public school is as good _____ of any private school.

- A. Or better than
- B. As or better that
- C. As or better than that
- D. As or better than those

The sentence above compares the equality of two schools that was public and private school. The best answer to complete the sentence was in option C. Some students got confused of the other options maybe because their focus only in the word 'better' that defined comparative form.

Number 26 was about verb (appendix FQ02). For example:

He knows to repair the carburetor without taking the whole car apart.

A B C D

The verb 'knows' should be changed in past form 'knew' to explain that the subject 'He' already know how to repair the carburetor of the car. Some students didn't choose option A because they thought there was no problem with the verb 'knows' which changed the meaning of the sentence.

Number 30 was about possessive pronoun (appendix FQ02). For example:

Each of the students in the accounting class has to type their own research paper.

A B C D

The problem in this sentence was in the possessive pronoun in option C. It should be changed according to the subject. The possessive pronoun 'their' should be changed with 'she/he' to agree with the subject of the sentence. Some students get lost with the option A the word 'students' made them think there was no problem with the possessive pronoun 'their'.

Number 6 was about dependent clause (appendix FQ02). For example:

Many of the international problems we are now facing ____.

- A. Linguistic incompetencies
- B. Are the result of misunderstanding
- C. Are because of not understanding themselves
- D. Lacks of the intelligent capabilities of understanding each other

Option B was the best answer to complete the sentence. The word 'are' in the sentence refers to the 'problems' in previous sentence and the function of the sentence in option B as complement.

Number 10 was about word choice (appendix FQ02). For example:

A fire in the ____ building could be a problem for firefighters.

- A. Ninety-story-tall
- B. Ninety-tall-story
- C. Ninety-stories-tall
- D. Ninety stories

The best answer for the question above was option A. The phrase 'ninety-story-tall' functions as an adjective to modify the noun 'building'. The word 'story' was still singular because it was a part of the whole adjective that modifies noun.

Number 20 was about superlative (appendix FQ02). For example:

Their office consisted of three rooms, ____ was used as a conference room.

- A. Larger of which
- B. The largest of which
- C. The largest of them
- D. Largest

The best choice to complete the sentence above was option B because the superlative determined which one was the largest from the three rooms.

Number 21 was about word choice (appendix FQ02). For example:

The word between should be changed with among. It was because the use of the word between to explain the position in the middle of two things, meanwhile the word among was the preposition to explain one thing in the middle of more than two things in a place.

Number 40 was about word choice (appendix FQ02). For example:

There are a large supply of pens and notebooks in the storeroom to the left of the
 A B C D
 library entrance.

The word are in option A should be change with singular word was as a linking verb for the phrase a large supply of pens.

Number 2 was about superlative (appendix FQ02). For example:

The fact that space exploration has increased dramatically in the past thirty years_____.

A. Is an evidence of us wanting to know more of our solar system
 B. Indicates that we are very eager to learn all we can about our solar system
 C. How we want to learn more about the solar system
 D. Is pointing to evidence of our intention to know a lot more about what is called our solar system

The best choice to complete the sentence above was in option B as a dependent clause to support the main clause.

Number 11 was about dependent clause (appendix FQ02). For example:

A major problem is the construction of new buildings ____.

A. Is that windows have been eliminated while air conditioning systems have not been perfected.
 B. Is they have eliminated windows and still don't have good air conditioning
 C. Is because windows are eliminated but air conditioners don't work good
 D. Is dependent on the fact that they have eliminated windows, they are not capable to produce efficient air conditioning systems

The best dependent clause to complete the sentence above was in option A as a supporting sentence to make the whole sentence meaningful.

Number 18 was about word choice (appendix FQ02). For example:

The death toll would ___ much higher if immediate action had not been taken.

A. Probably being
 B. Probably be
 C. Probably been
 D. Be probable

The best choice to complete the sentence above was option B. Because of the modal 'would', the appropriate phrase was 'probably be'. The linking verb 'be' was in the base form after the modal would.

Number 35 was about was about possessive pronoun (appendix FQ02). For example:

Some of us have to study their lessons more carefully if we expect to pass this
 A B C D
 examination.

The proper possessive pronoun to change option B was 'our', because the word 'us' refers to the subject 'we' (some of us). From the discussion above, it could be seen that the English grammatical aspects still be the most difficult problems that caused the low scores in TOEFL Mock Test. In session

2 about structure and written expression, most of the students made mistakes in choosing the right grammatical aspect that suits to the meaning of the sentence.

From the data above, the grammatical aspects of word choice and verbs were very crucial for the students to choose the right answer. The lack of grammatical knowledge was the problem that caused the students to understand the sentence correctly. It needed critical analysis to make a good choice over confusing multiple choices.

The Results of Postgraduate Students

The table below shows all students of Law Studies Postgraduates who already joined the test and already had the results.

Table 1 – List of Scores Achieved by the Test Takers

NO	NAME	SCORES		PASSED /FAILED	PERCENTAGE
		RESULT	STANDARD		
1	X1	467	425	PASSED	45% of students passed the test
2	X2	337	425	FAILED	
3	X3	563	425	PASSED	
4	X4	377	425	FAILED	
5	X5	507	425	PASSED	
6	X6	363	425	FAILED	
7	X7	327	425	FAILED	
8	X8	387	425	FAILED	
9	X9	317	425	FAILED	
10	X10	323	425	FAILED	
11	X11	327	425	FAILED	
12	X12	450	425	PASSED	
13	X13	493	425	PASSED	
14	X14	490	425	PASSED	
15	X15	370	425	FAILED	
16	X16	377	425	FAILED	
17	X17	477	425	PASSED	
18	X18	533	425	PASSED	
19	X19	513	425	PASSED	
20	X20	330	425	FAILED	

The standard score for postgraduate students at UNDANA University is 425. This score is quite high to be achieved. It needs more focus, critical analysis to have a good comprehension before choosing the best answer over the confusing multiple choices.

There are 20 students of Law Study had taken the TOEFL MOCK Test, however, only 9 of 20 students passed the test. The rest of the students have to do the second test and have to have the standard score of postgraduate program before thesis examination. It takes extra effort to pass the second test as the requirement before graduation.

Figure 1 – Score Graphics of Test Result

The graph above presented the data in table 4 to make it easy to analyze how many students have gained the best scores and how many students have failed. From the graph, it can be seen that the range of the scores are not too bad to be compared to the determined scores. The lowest score was 330 and the highest score was 563, while the determined standard score that was given by postgraduate program was 425. Half of the students have the average scores that requires them to have critical thinking and critical analysis to choose the right answer among the choices. It can be easier if they already mastered the grammar of the language.

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, the analysis of the TOEFL Mock Test results for Law Studies Postgraduate students at UNDANA University highlights the significance of English grammatical aspects in achieving a good score. The majority of students struggled with choosing the correct grammatical aspect, particularly in word choice and verb usage, which led to low scores.

The standard score of 425 set by the university is a challenging target, and only 9 out of 20 students managed to pass the test. The results emphasize the need for students to focus on improving their grammatical knowledge and critical analysis skills to excel in the test. By mastering English grammar and developing critical thinking, students can increase their chances of achieving the required score and ultimately, successfully completing their postgraduate program.

Based on the conclusion above, the following benefits can be offered to the academic world. (1) Improved Language Instruction: The study highlights the importance of English grammatical aspects in achieving a good score in the TOEFL Mock Test. Therefore, language instructors can focus on developing more effective teaching methods to improve students' grammatical knowledge and critical analysis skills. (2) Enhanced Assessment Tools: The research suggests that the TOEFL Mock Test can be a valuable assessment tool to identify areas where students need improvement. Academic institutions can use this test to evaluate students' language proficiency and provide targeted support to those who struggle. Next, (3) better Preparation for Postgraduate Studies: The study emphasizes the need for postgraduate students to achieve a high score in the TOEFL Mock Test to meet the university's standard. By providing students with the necessary language skills and critical thinking abilities, academic institutions can better prepare them for postgraduate studies.

The last, (4) informing Language Policy: The research can inform language policy decisions at the university level, highlighting the importance of language proficiency in academic success. This can

lead to the development of more effective language policies that support students' academic achievement. By recognizing the significance of English grammatical aspects in academic success, the academic world can take steps to improve language instruction, assessment, and policy, ultimately enhancing students' overall academic performance.

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